

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Improved medium for efficient anther culture of some indica rice hybrids

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Anther culture of high heterotic F₁ hybrid rices could be used to isolate doubled-haploid true breeding lines. Assuming that heterosis in rice is due primarily to dispersion of genes in parents that display directional dominance, some doubled-haploid lines derived from heterotic F₁s theoretically should equal F₁ hybrid performance. Such doubled-haploid lines could be used for commercial cultivation or as parents of second-cycle F₁ hybrids.

To test the validity of this assumption, we cultured anthers of four IRRI-bred heterotic F₁ hybrids.

An improved culture medium increased anther culture efficiency in the F₁ hybrids tested. Two media formulations differing in source of N were used (Table 1). Medium MSN is a

Table 1. Media composition.^a

Constituent	SK-1 (mg/liter)	MSN (mg/liter)
KNO ₃	3150	2830
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	—	463
KH ₂ PO ₄	540	170
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	150	440
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	185	185
MnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	22.3	4.4
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10	1.5
H ₃ BO ₃	6	6.2
KI	1	0.8
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.25	0.25
CuSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.025	0.025

^aConstituents (mg/liter) in common: 27.85 Na₂·EDTA + 37.25 Fe·SO₄·7H₂O; 2 glycine; 100 inositol; 2.5 niacin; 2.5 thianine HCl; 2.5 pyridoxine; 500 casein hydrolysate; 0.75 2, 4-D; 2.5 NAA; 0.75 kinetin; 40,000 sucrose; 8,000 agar. The generation medium consisted of MS basal medium supplemented with 1 mg NAA, 1 mg BAP, 0.5 mg kinetin, 30,000 mg sucrose/liter.

Table 2. Callus induction and green plant regeneration in anther calli of hybrid rices induced in SK-1 and MSN media.

Hybrid ^a	Anthers plated (no.)	Anther calli		Calli transferred (no.)	Calli regenerating			
		no.	%		Green plants		Albino plants	
					no.	%	no.	%
<i>SK-1</i>								
H-1	2216	146	6.1	114	42	36.8	27	23.6
H-2	1698	82	4.8	52	23	44.2	20	38.4
H-4	2855	308	10.7	220	74	33.6	55	25.0
H-5	1572	69	4.3	41	5	12.2	4	9.7
Total	8401	605	7.2	427	144	33.7	106	24.8
<i>MSN</i>								
H-1	2147	298	13.8	278	20	7.1	65	23.3
H-2	2495	275	11.0	228	15	6.5	45	19.1
H-4	2900	406	14.0	284	55	19.3	80	28.1
H-5	2176	125	5.7	69	6	8.6	12	17.3
Total	9718	1104	11.3	859	96	11.1	202	23.5

^aH-1 = hybrid 1 (IR54752 A/IR2797-125-3-3-2 R), H-2 = hybrid 2 (IR54752 A/IR64 R), H-4 = hybrid 4 (IR54752 A/ARC11353 R), H-5 = hybrid 5 (IR46830 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R).

blend of Murashige and Skoog's and Chinese N6. SK-1 contains N, mainly as nitrate, among other modifications. Vitamins, amino acids, sucrose, and hormones were similar for both media.

Response (% anthers producing visible calli) was better in MSN medium for all the hybrids (Table 2), in some cases more than twice that in SK-1. In the regeneration medium, however, calli induced in SK-1 averaged 200% higher regeneration of green plants. In IR54752 A/IR2797-125-3-3-2 R and IR54752 A/IR64 R, the difference was 400%.

Among 859 anther calli induced in MSN, 96 green plant-regenerating calli were identified. As many as 144 green plant-regenerating calli were obtained from only 427 calli induced in SK-1.

Other media formulations also were tested. In all, more than 35,000 anthers were cultured, resulting in more than 300 green plant-regenerating anther calli. About 700 plants transferred to the field reached maturity.

The SK-1 culture medium appears promising for alleviating the poor anther culture efficiency of indica rices. □

Optimum distance of isolation for hybrid rice seed production

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Maintaining purity of parental lines and F₁ hybrid seed is the most important factor in hybrid seed production. One way to maintain seed purity is to adequately isolate plots used for producing hybrid seed.

We laid out an experiment at IRRI 1987-88 to determine the isolation

distance that would prevent contamination. A seed production plot of IR64 (1,250 m²) was used as the pollen source. At 10 d before flowering, eight potted plants of the CMS line IR54752 A were placed at different distances (0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200, 225 m) in two directions (northeast and northwest) from the pollen source (per anticipated wind direction during flowering). Weather records for the experimental periods of both years are given in Table 1.

Pollen fertility was measured at flowering and four plants showing

Table 1. Weather record for rice flowering period at Los Baños (Agroclimatic Data Bank, IRRI).

Season	Flowering period (d)	Maximum temperature (°C)	Wind ^a		Relative humidity
			Speed (m/s)	Direction	
1987 WS (20-29 Nov)	1	23.9	2.1	ENE	55
	2	24.4	1.6	VRBL	78
	3	23.6	1.4	VRBL	81
	4	23.0	1.4	ESE	70
	5	24.0	1.3	NE	64
	6	24.2	1.7	NE	60
	7	22.9	5.2	WNW	62
	8	21.1	3.9	ENE	70
	9	23.0	1.7	SSE	57
	10	23.0	1.2	ESE	63
1988 DS (16-25 May)	1	36.2	1.2	NNW	42
	2	37.0	1.0	VRBL	34
	3	35.4	1.2	SE	42
	4	37.0	1.4	E	34
	5	36.5	1.1	S	42
	6	35.6	1.2	E	45
	7	35.0	0.9	VRBL	48
	8	36.5	1.2	SE	39
	9	33.4	1.1	NE	60
	10	34.5	1.2	NE	50

^a Expected wind direction in November and May is NE.

Table 2. Effect of distance between restorer line (R) and CMS line on outcrossing rate. IRRI, 1987 WS and 1988 DS.

Direction of CMS line in relation to pollen source	Distance (m) of CMS line from pollen source	Seed set ^a (%)	
		1987 WS	1988 DS
NE	0 (control)	9.2	8.6
	25	7.2	7.0
	50	6.0	5.0
	75	5.6	2.0
	100	5.0	0.5
	125	4.1	0.0
	150	3.8	0.0
NW	175	3.1	0.0
	200	2.4	0.0
	225	2.0	0.0
	0 (control)	6.0	4.0
	25	5.3	3.1
	50	5.1	1.2
	75	4.0	0.3
100	3.3	0.0	
125	2.1	0.0	
150	0.8	0.0	
175	0.0	0.0	
200	0.0	0.0	
225	0.0	0.0	

^a Av of 4 replications.

complete pollen sterility were retained per distance (each plant represented one replication). The potted plants were kept in the field for 10 d (20-29 Nov in 1987 wet season [WL] and 16-25 May in 1988 dry season [DS]) to synchronize with flowering of the pollen source. No other flowering rice crop was around the field for more than 500 m in any direction. Distance pollen traveled was determined

by seed setting on open-pollinated panicles of the CMS line.

In 1987 WS, seed set on CMS plants up to 225 m distance in the northeast direction and up to 150 m in the northwest direction (Table 2). In 1988 DS, seed set on CMS plants up to 100 m in the northeast direction and up to 75 m in the northwest direction. Pollen traveled farther in WS than in

DS, perhaps because of higher wind velocity (1.2-5.2 m/s in WS, 0.9-1.4 m/s in DS). Higher temperature, lower relative humidity, and unfavorable wind direction in DS may have cut the distance pollen could travel. Under Los Baños conditions, a safe isolation distance would be 125 m in DS and 250 m in WS. □

CNA-IRAT 4, a new CMS indica rice population

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CNPAP and Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrières (IRAT) have created an indica population that segregates for a monogenic recessive male sterile gene obtained by mutation on IR36 by R. J. Singh and H. Ikehashi.

Nine varieties were crossed and backcrossed to IR36 as the male parent to achieve sterile plants (see table). F₂ seeds of each backcross were bulked to

CNA-IRAT 4 population composition.

Variety	Parentage	Outcrossing rate (%)
IR36 (ms ms)	IR1561-228-1-2/IR1737//CR94-13	25.00
BG90-2	IR262/Remadja	8.33
CNA7	T141/IR665-1-175-3	8.33
CNA3815	CICA4/BG90-2/SML 5617	8.33
CNA3848	5461//IR36/CICA7	8.33
CNA3887	4440//BG90-2/Tetep	8.33
Colombia 1	Napal/Takao Iku 18	8.33
Eloni	IR454/SML KAPURI//SML 66H10	8.33
Nanicao	Brazilian germplasm	8.33
UPR103-80-1-2	IR24/Cauvery	8.33

form the initial population, CNA-IRAT 4/0/0.

Outcrossed seeds collected on male sterile plants of that population were bulked to form the next population, CNA-IRAT 4/0/1. The procedure was

repeated four times to obtain the CNA-IRAT 4/0/4 population.

Seeds of the CNA-IRAT 4/0/4 population are available to rice breeders. □